

Kinetics of Discharge of Cadmium at the Dropping Mercury Electrode

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The reduction of Cd (II) in ethylthioglycolate (ETG) has been studied polarographically in different non-aqueous solvents such as ethanol and dioxane. In both the solvents the reduction of cadmium-ETG has been found to be irreversible and diffusion controlled. The values of kinetic parameters-formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^0$, and transfer coefficient α has been calculated by Koutecky's theoretical treatment as extended by Mites and Israel.

Mercapto acids and other sulphur containing compounds have a wide variety of applications varying from biological, pharmaceutical activity to analytical and other chemical uses, and therefore the importance of this group of compounds has grown. The polarographic behaviour of several such compounds viz. thiomalic acid¹, β -mercapto propionic acid², thiolactic acid³ and 3-mercapto-1,2-propanediol and their metal complexes⁵⁻¹² have already been studied in these laboratories by Saxena and co-workers. There is, however, no reference in the literature to the polarographic study of Cd-ethylthioglycolate system and hence the present investigation has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethylthioglycolate (97% Evan's chemetics Inc., New York) and reagent grade chemicals were used without further purification. Stock solution of ethylthioglycolate was prepared in absolute alcohol and in dioxan separately. Triton X-100 was used as maximum suppressor. NaClO_4 was used as supporting electrolyte. Ammonia-ammonium nitrate buffer (0.4 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.4$ M NH_4NO_3) was used to adjust the pH of the solution. All solutions used in polarographic measurements had, in addition to ethylthioglycolate, cadmium ion concentration of 1.0 mM, 0.5 M NaClO_4 , 0.002% Triton X-100 and buffer (0.4 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.4$ M NH_4NO_3) in each 40% non-aqueous solvent. The ETG concentration was varied from 0.02 M to 0.04 M.

A Cambridge (General purpose) polarograph was used in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell ($25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$). The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m = 1.950$ mg/sec. at a height of 60 cm. of Hg and drop time $t = 3.22$ sec. vs. S.C.E. All potentials were referred to the saturated calomel electrode.

Universal thermostat U_3 type (German) was used for controlling the temperature.

For determination of kinetic parameters the current at the end of the drop life was recorded instead of the average current, because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on the Koutecky's calculations which are more accurately reproduced by measuring maximum current¹³. The effect of height of mercury column on the diffusion current has been studied to determine the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction. Necessary correction for IR drop and residual current were applied to determine the half wave potential and diffusion current data respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In both the solvents, the plots of i_d as a function of square root of the height of mercury reservoir was found to be linear and passes through the origin, indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the wave.

In the absence of dissolved oxygen Cd^{2+} produces a single well-defined reduction wave in both of the solvents (Fig. 1, curves A-D, Fig. 2, curves A-D). The shift, towards the negative side in the half-wave potential, with the increasing concentration of ethylthioglycolate indicates the possibility of complex formation. Conventional log plots showed that the reduction of Cd^{2+} in ethylthioglycolate media corresponds to an irreversible process. The logarithmic plot yields a straight line whose resulting slopes were not agreeing with the theoretical value for two electron transfer process, indicating the irreversible reduction of Cd^{2+} in ethylthioglycolate solution and hence it was found expedient to apply Koutecky's¹³ theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel¹⁴ for evaluating the kinetic parameters (Transfer coefficient, α and formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ at 0.2412 vs. S.C.E.) which is based on a plot of $E_{d,e}$ vs. $\log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)}$ and may be constructed as for a reversible wave.

The mathematical solution for an electrode reaction at the d.m.e controlled by the kinetics of the electron transfer is given by

$$i/i_d = F(X) \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$X = \left(\frac{12}{7} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} K_{f,h} \frac{t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (2)$$

in which ' t ' is the drop time, D_0 is the diffusion coefficient of electroactive substance, $K_{f,h}$ is the potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant described by

$$K_{f,h} = K_{f,h}^\circ \exp [\alpha n F (E + 0.2412) / RT] \quad \dots (3)$$

where E is referred to S.C.E., i and i_d are the currents at the actual flow at the end of the drop life at potential E and on the plateau of the wave respectively.

From the value of i/i_d at various selected potentials the corresponding values of functions ' X ' may be obtained from the original table of Koutecky. Plotting

log X vs. $E_{d.e.}$ then permits values for $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ and αn to be secured. For this purpose it is convenient to combine preceding equation with

$$\log_{10}(X) = \log_{10}(12/7)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{K_{f,h}^{\circ} t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\alpha n F (E + 0.2412)}{2.303 RT} \quad \dots (4)$$

Thus a plot of log X vs. $E_{d.e.}$ shall be linear; $E = 0$ (vs. N.H.E. or -0.2412 vs. S.C.E.) the value of $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ can be obtained. Meanwhile αn is obtained from the slope of the line.

Fig. 1. Polarogram of 1.0 mM Cd^{2+} in different concentrations of ethylthioglycolate in ethanol [A, 0.8 mM; B 10.0 mM; C, 20 mM; D, 40 mM].

The amount of labour involved in the process is excessive. Meites and Israel¹⁴ have shown that labour can be considerably decreased by taking advantage of the fact that for value of i/i_a between 0.1 to 0.95, Koutecky's values for X and i/i_a correspond to a linear relationship between log X and $\frac{i}{(i_a - i)}$. Thus the equation of a totally irreversible wave at 25° becomes

$$E_{d.e.} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^{\circ} t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_a - i)} \quad \dots (5)$$

which may be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_a - i)} \quad \dots (6)$$

with

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^{\circ} t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (7)$$

($E_{d.e.}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are referred to S.C.E.).

The kinetic parameters of Cd-ETG system in both the solvents were calculated by using equations 6 and 7. The value of αn was obtained from slope $\frac{-0.0542}{\alpha n}$ of the straight line of $E_{d,e}$, vs. $\log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)}$. The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, which

Fig. 2. Polarogram of 1.0 mM Cd²⁺ in different concentrations of ethylthioglycolate in dioxane.

[A, 0.0 mM; B, 10 mM; C, 20 mM; D, 40 mM].

was used to calculate $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ at different concentrations of the ligand (tables 1 and 2). Since ' i ' does not vary appreciably over the range of potential covered by the rising part of the wave due to complexed Cd²⁺ ion, it was not considered necessary to apply the correction for ' i '¹⁵.

TABLE 1

Values of diffusion current, diffusion coeff., $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ and αn at 25° in Ethanol

Concentration of ligand (mM)	i_d (μA)	D_0^{\dagger} (cm ² /sec)	Slope from log plots (volts)	Intercept $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts)	αn	$K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ (cm/sec)
10	11.85	5.212×10^{-5}	0.081	0.884	0.664	1.658×10^{-12}
20	13.00	2.824×10^{-5}	0.069	0.928	0.782	8.954×10^{-14}
40	11.00	1.196×10^{-5}	0.064	0.974	0.846	5.833×10^{-18}

TABLE 2

Values of diffusion current, diffusion coefficient, $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ and αn at 25° in Dioxan

Concentration of ligand (mM)	i_d (μA)	D_0^{\dagger} (cm ² /sec)	Slope from log plots (volts)	Intercept $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (volts)	αn	$K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ (cm/sec)
10	9.70	4.215×10^{-5}	0.105	0.860	0.516	1.211×10^{-10}
20	11.30	2.456×10^{-5}	0.088	0.946	0.615	1.613×10^{-11}
40	10.60	1.152×10^{-5}	0.084	0.998	0.649	3.243×10^{-12}

Tables 1 and 2 show that the values of $K_{f,h}^{\circ}$ and αn are affected by the concentration of the ligand as well as the solvent. The value of rate constants affected by the concentration of the ligand, is due to the shift in half wave potential with the increase in the concentration of complexing agent.

The magnitude of the slope, as well as the shape of the curves and values of rate constants indicate that the cathodic depolarization of Cd-ethylthioglycolate system in both the solvents, proceeds in irreversible manner. The values of rate constants in dioxan medium was found to be greater than in ethanol medium.

It is apparent from the above study that Cd^{2+} is reduced irreversibly (at d.m.e.) in ethylthioglycolate at 0.5 *M* ionic strength and in ethanolic as well as in dioxan media. The reduction is diffusion controlled in both solvents.

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